

5th HOUSE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE

M. Nalina Segaran* & Dr. M. Mahalakshmi**

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

The 5th house is symbolic of the first conception or pregnancy. It also has to do with artistic talents, fancies, tastes and property derived through the wife or the luck of a business partner. The 5th house also denotes entertainment, recreation, sports, romance, amusements and other similar interests.

Key Words: Birth, Romancing, Beloved

Introduction:

Every house in the horoscope carries a unique meaning and represents a specific area of life. Indeed, the twelve houses are truly what makes astrology so spectacular. How these houses work is fairly complex, but we will make it easy for you to understand what the 5th house in Kundli is all about. The signs and planets associated with the 5th house Jupiter is the natural signification of this house. It is best for Jupiter, Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury but a weak house for Saturn.

5th House Significance:

A strong 5th house indicates strong character and judgment (the discernment from keen, clear intelligence), happiness from good children, and spiritual learnedness. It is the house of poorva punya, 'past life credit', from righteous (dharmic) acts of merit accumulated from past lives.

What happens when 5th house is activated?

The 5th house tells us about the wisdom and knowledge which you have gained through your own efforts. We study this house when we have to know about the success or failure in the interview. In spite of knowledge & wisdom, people fail to get a government job if this house is not activated. The 5th house represents pleasure, sex, and fun. It represents that aspect of a relationship that's exciting, light, and playful. It's mostly related to physical love and the romantic pleasures of this world.

What does your 5th house rule?

The Fifth House rules creativity, self-expression, recreation, relationships, and offspring. It's also known as the House of Pleasure because the Fifth House revolves around both sensual desire and pure, child likes fun.

What if 5th house is weak?

The 5th house in astrology denotes children, your pursuit towards pleasures, hobbies, love tendencies and creative self-expression. Now understand that this house does not signify the marriage, but if your 5th house is weak, you cannot do justice to your 7th house in terms of Love and enjoying pleasure.

About 5th House in Vedic Astrology:

The 5th house in Kundli or horoscope is linked to creativity, romance and children. It is all about what makes you feel good. Pleasure is often an output of the creative activities you indulge in. It is also considered the House of Luck. Studying the planets in the 5th house will reveal how you might fare when it comes to games of chance, such as a lottery. This house is also connected to the affairs of the heart. Analyzing the planetary positions and signs in the 5th house can reveal how you deal with these matters. Bringing children into the world is also a creative process. The 5th house is symbolic of the first conception or pregnancy. It also has to do with artistic talents, fancies, tastes and property derived through the wife or the luck of a business partner. The 5th house also denotes entertainment, recreation, sports, romance, amusements and other similar interests. Being a trine house in kundli, the 5th house indicates the purva punya sthana which indicates the meritorious deeds of one's previous life. Games of chances such as lottery, gambling, puzzles, cards, shares, betting and the stock exchange indicate the 5th house. The body part associated with the 5th house is the stomach, where we are nourished, and from which we create everything. Feeling full, creative and content with life is the fifth house as shown by this body part. The 5th house is also linked with the mind and mental health.

Fundamentals of 5th House in Kundli:

Vedic name of 5th House: Putra Bhava

Natural Ruling Planet and Sign: Sun and Leo

Body parts associated: Stomach, pancreas, spine, upper and lower back

People in 5th House: Children, romantic partners, students, artists, creative partners, and others we love and adore

Activities in 5th House: When we express our heart's desire, we act through the 5th house. Creating art, teaching or learning what you love, romancing your beloved, giving an astrology reading or healing session are all examples of 5th house activities.

Planets in 5th House of Kundli: Significance and Effects:

Sun in 5th House: The Sun in the 5th House is a wonderful placement as it illuminates the creative mind with immense passion. You will have a strong desire to express your creativity through writing, drama, art, sports and romance. This placement also inflates the ego and causes overconfidence. A strong Sun in this house indicates a shining career for your children. But if your Sun is weak in this house, you will remain tense and worried about them.

Moon in 5th House: The placement of Moon in this house represents inclinations, creativity, children, romance, gains and income from investments. Moon is the planet of creativity, and the 5th house rules over the perception of pleasure and self-satisfaction through artistic expression. An afflicted Moon will reduce all the good effects and you may worry about your child's education. You may also remain depressed.

Jupiter in 5th House: Jupiter, the planet of wisdom, makes for an excellent teacher who is a natural guide. You will have a strong penchant to pass on your wisdom to others, especially children. This placement is also excellent for wealth, investments and career. However, avoid excessive gambling and speculation.

Venus in 5th House: Venus in the 5th House will bless you with great artistic talent. You will be a connoisseur of fine arts. If you have children, they will be similarly inclined. The need for close company is strong; you desire love and attention. The placement of Venus in this house also suggests benefits through speculation, but you should be careful while making decisions.

Mars in 5th House: Natives with Mars in the 5th house show a strong desire to express their creativity. They are highly skilled in sports. This placement will cause problems for children. You love competition, especially related to physical disciplines. The 5th house also represents investments, and when Mars resides in this house there is a possibility of the native dabbling in speculation or even becoming a gambler, depending on how strong the planet is. Be careful; gambling could introduce untold problems in your life.

Mercury in 5th House: For natives with Mercury in the 5th house, your mind is a major creative too. You communicate well and have a flair for writing, which make for fulfilling hobbies or successful careers. You are intelligent, creative, innovative and optimistic. You are fond of mental games -- anything that stimulates and challenges your analytical mind. This placement will make you inclined towards brains over beauty.

Saturn in 5th House: A Kundli with Saturn in the 5th house will make the native feel a certain lack of love and appreciation in life. You will often struggle to express yourself, both emotionally and creatively. Relationships in your life are often serious, lacking romance and spontaneity. You come across as a cold person. To enjoy healthy and balanced relationships, you should work on this inability to express your emotions to those who matter.

Raghu in 5th House: Natives with Raghu in the 5th house have a strong desire for recognition in privileged roles that allow them to be in the limelight. Literary persons, theatre artists and politicians will benefit from this placement. You take on all the roles required to climb the ladder of success. This Raghu position creates problems in one's relationship with the children or father.

Kethu in 5th House: Kethu's presence in the 5th house in Kundli will make you philosophical. You will be quick to learn new languages. You will be fluent in many foreign languages. Financial gains from speculation are likely. However, this placement may bring a lack of emotional satisfaction in your life. Afflicted Kethu can bring adverse results to children and also prove unfavorable for your health.

Analysis:

I have used Natal chart information used are as below:

Mars	Raghu		Sat Moon
			Jupiter
Lagnam Mercury Venus	Sun	Kethu	

Conclusion:

In reality 5th House plays a vital role in Astrology in the event of entertainment, recreation, sports, romance, amusements and other similar interests.

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